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**AWARENESS OF STUDENT TEACHERS TOWARDS
ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION WITH REGARD
TO FREQUENT USAGE OF SOCIAL MEDIA**

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Abstract

The present study is an attempt to examine the awareness towards environmental education among student teachers with regard to frequent usage of social media. The study was conducted through the descriptive survey method of research on a sample of 300 student teachers with the help of Awareness towards Environmental Education Scale which is developed and validated by the investigator(2019). Three Hundred student teachers studying in 10 colleges of education of Sankarankovil Taluk of Tenkasi District in Tamil Nadu were chosen as the sample, by using simple random sampling technique. The percentage and the 't' values were calculated for comparing the opinions of the respondents on the Awareness towards Environmental Education Scale. The major finding of the study is that the student teachers who are not using social media frequently have better awareness towards environmental education than the student teachers who are not using social media frequently.

Keywords: Social Media, Environmental Education, student teachers

Introduction

Environmental Education is defined in its broadest sense to encompass raising awareness, acquiring new perspectives, values, knowledge and skills, and formal and informal processes leading to changed behaviour in support of an ecologically sustainable environment. The position of environmental education on the curriculum and the view of the teaching have changed a great deal in recent years. Formerly, it was first and foremost the Biology teacher who had environmental education as a theme. Whereas, today it is a theme which all the subjects on the curriculum in theory are obliged to deal with, the amount depending on where it fits in naturally. From there, environmental education motivates and empowers students to take responsibility for their local environment. Environmental Education challenges learners to engage with the environmental, social, cultural, and economic influences that shape the future of the planet and people's role within it. The United Nations Decade of Education for Sustainable Development 2005-2014 emphasizes the need not only to inform and educate people so they can make the right decisions, but to ensure that such education is propelled by an underlying ethical reasoning. It is timely, global efforts to save the planet often remind us of our need for ethics. Many environmental conventions and treaties have come up in recent years to ring the ethics bell even louder. People around the world want better relationships between themselves, within communities, between communities and between nations. And they know that this includes relationships between humans and the more than human world, or for others, between humans and the rest of creation. In using the term "more - than - human world" we suggest that exploring new relationships with Earth not only benefits human beings and their needs, but also the needs and well-being of forests, fields, rivers, animals, creatures in the sea and the atmosphere. Social media and social networks, from Facebook to Snapshot to Twitter and beyond, are an increasingly important part of how we communicate and connect day to day. They're key for staying in touch and up-to-date as well as contributing to our world and being creative. Many teachers find social networking a great way to expand their personal learning network and to discover resources.

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Need and Importance of the Study

Educating the people, particularly the youth about the environment and its related aspects helps to link the learning process with daily life experiences, thus making it more meaningful. One of the greatest problems facing the earth at present is the impact of humans on environment. Experts argue that the environmental problems caused by human development, such as global warming, the destruction of rainforests and threats to bio-diversity, have reached an unprecedented scale and complexity in world history. According to Hollweg et al. (2011), an environmentally literate person is someone who "makes informed decisions concerning the environment; is willing to act on these decisions...and participates in civic life" (pp. 2-3). However, people hold many misconceptions about the environment (Coyle, 2005). Environmental education (EE) provides the methods and content that can lead to environmental literacy and a more sustainable future. Through EE, people develop questioning, analysis and interpretation skills; knowledge of environmental processes and systems; skills for understanding and addressing environmental issues; and personal and civic responsibility (NAAEE, 2010). Spread of environmental knowledge and awareness of environmental issues requires certain tools of communication, offline or online. Social media tools are gaining importance in increasing environmental concern and environmental responsible behaviors in public. (Krätzig & Warren-Kretzschmar, 2014). Social media (e.g. Facebook, Twitter, whatsapp, instagram etc.) permit users to generate and exchange of user generated contents on different themes. Online space is provided to users for interaction by Social networking sites (SSNs). Thus social media can be used as an enabler to create awareness of environmental issues. In India, from school studies to college studies, most of youth learn and write exams on environmental education. Most of the school and college students learn environmental education without any having any understanding of environmental issues. They learn environmental education only for scoring marks and getting degree. Environmental education was mandated as a compulsory subject in all schools across the country by the Supreme Court of India in 1991 following the filing of a PIL (public interest litigation) by M.C. Mehta, India's leading environmental lawyer and recipient of the Magsaysay and Goldman awards. The University Grants Commission (UGC) has recently instructed its universities and colleges to introduce a compulsory six-module. In Tamilnadu, Tamilnadu Teachers Education University included Environmental Education as optional subject in Teacher Education Curriculum at UG level. Though most of the student teachers have awareness towards environmental education, the extent of awareness towards environmental education may varied with regard to frequent usage of social media. With this background, the investigator wants to study the awareness towards environmental education among student teachers.

Objectives of the Study

- To find out the level of awareness towards environmental education among students teachers with regard to frequent usage of social media.
- To find out whether there is any significant difference between student teachers who are using social media frequently and those who are not using social media frequently in their awareness towards environmental education.

Hypothesis of the Study

- There is no significant difference between student teachers who are using social media frequently and those who are not using social media frequently in their awareness towards environmental education.

Methodology

The study was conducted through the descriptive survey method of research on a sample of 300 student teachers with the help of Awareness towards Environmental Education Scale which is developed and validated by the investigator (2019). Three Hundred student teachers studying in 10 colleges of simple random sampling technique. The percentage and the 't' values were calculated for comparing the opinions of the respondents on the Awareness towards Environmental Education Scale.

Descriptive Analysis of Data

Table - 1

Level of Awareness towards Environmental Education among Students Teachers with Regard to Frequent Usage of Social Media

Variable	Frequent Usage of Social Media	Low		Average		High	
		Count	%	Count	%	Count	%
Awareness towards environmental education	Yes	17	9.5	134	74.9	28	15.6
	No	28	23.1	79	65.3	14	11.6

It is inferred from the above table that, 74.9% of student teachers who are using social media frequently have average level of awareness towards environmental education. And also, 65.3% student teachers who are not using social media frequently have average level of awareness towards environmental education.

Inferential Analysis of Data

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference between student teachers who are using social media frequently and those who are not using social media frequently in their awareness towards environmental education.

Table - 2

t-test showing the Significance Difference in Awareness towards Environmental Education among Student Teachers with regard to Frequent Usage of Social Media

Variable	Frequent usage of social media	N	Mean	S.D	calculated value	Table value	Remarks
Awareness towards environmental education	Yes	179	1.20492	18.98176	4.885	1.96	S
	No	121	1.08142	23.00301			

For df (298) at 5% level of significant = 1.96

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated "t" value (4.885) is than greater than table value (1.96) for df (298) at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. It indicates that there is significant difference between student teachers who are using social media frequently and those who are not using social media frequently in their awareness towards environmental education. From the mean difference in the table-1, it is observed that, the student teachers who are not using social media frequently have better awareness towards environmental education than their counterpart.

Findings of the Study

The findings from the descriptive analysis revealed that 74.9% of student teachers who are using social media frequently have average level of awareness towards environmental education. And also, 65.3% student teachers who are not using social media frequently have average level of awareness towards environmental education. The findings from inferential analysis that the student teachers who are not using social media frequently have better awareness towards environmental education than the student teachers who are not using social media frequently.

Conclusion

It was found out from the data analysed that the student teachers who are not using social media frequently have better awareness towards environmental education than the student teachers who are not using social media frequently. It clearly indicates that the frequent usage of social media is not a factor in creating awareness towards environmental education. The student teachers may get awareness towards environmental education through studying the concepts in environmental education from school and college curriculum itself. The awareness towards environmental education is the stepping stone

towards changes in learning the concepts of environmental education by student teachers with sky-scraping curiosity and this may be useful in teaching the same concepts related to environmental education to their school students in future as prospective teachers.

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